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RESULTS**

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IS MASTERY DYING IN THE NAME OF COMPLETION?

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Abstract

Studies indicate that students are often promoted to higher grade levels due to policy requirements rather than demonstrated mastery, suggesting systemic factors that prioritize curriculum completion over learning depth. This quantitative descriptive-correlational study examined the profile of teacher-respondents, their perceptions of learners' challenges, and the instructional strategies used in teaching mathematical word problems among thirty Grade 4 to 6 teachers in Javier, Leyte, with data analyzed using ANOVA. Results showed that learners tend to rely on memorization, experience difficulties in comprehension, and display low confidence in word problems, while teachers reported repetitive instructional methods and accelerated pacing to meet curriculum expectations. These findings suggest that learners' limited performance is influenced by instructional and systemic factors emphasizing compliance and coverage. The study concludes that policy-based promotion and rigid curriculum pacing contribute to shallow learning outcomes. It is recommended that school supervision must shift from protecting teacher performance to protecting learner performance. Strict, unannounced monitoring, removal of scripted evaluations, accountability for training, and mastery-based promotion are the concrete steps that must be taken.

Keywords: mathematics problem solving, teaching strategies, learner performance, curriculum completion

INTRODUCTION

Education is meant to build mastery, yet many classrooms focus more on completing the curriculum than on ensuring understanding. This results in students moving to higher grade levels without fully developing the skills needed for problem solving. In mathematics, particularly in addition and multiplication, learners often depend on memorized steps instead of applying concepts in new situations (Hussein & Csikos, 2023; Yang, 2021).

Learners' performance in mathematics can be described in terms of conceptual understanding, computational skills, and problem comprehension. Weak conceptual understanding limits their ability to transfer knowledge beyond routine exercises (Powell, 2020). Many also lack fluency in computation, slowing them down and lowering their confidence (Capuyan, 2019). Problem comprehension is another barrier, as learners struggle to analyze word problems and identify the right operations, often leading to frustration (Fuchs, Fuchs, & Stecker, 2021).

Teachers respond to these struggles using teaching strategies such as instructional adaptability, remedial interventions, and motivational and emotional support. When teachers adjust lessons and provide remediation, learners improve in both reasoning and computation (Capuyan, 2019; Lumbao, 2022). Motivation also plays an important role. Praise, encouragement, and recognition foster persistence and confidence, allowing learners to overcome difficulties (Boaler,

2019; Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020). However, teachers often face systemic pressures that push them to move quickly through the curriculum, limiting their ability to focus on mastery (DepEd, 2021).

Recent Philippine studies provide strong evidence that the education system's emphasis on curriculum completion and grade promotion undermines true learner mastery. For example, consultations by Philippine Business for Education (PBE) revealed that 10–30% of students promoted to the next grade level do not meet basic competency or mastery in required subjects.

This research was conducted among Grades 4 to 6 mathematics teachers in Javier, Leyte. These respondents were chosen because they handle learners at a critical stage where mastery of addition and multiplication is expected, yet difficulties remain. By looking into teachers' profiles, their perceptions of learners' struggles, and their strategies, the study provides evidence on how teaching practices influence problem-solving performance.

Statement of the Problem

This study examines the relationship between the demographic profile of Grade 4 to 6 teachers in Javier, Leyte, and their perceptions of learner performance and teaching strategies in solving mathematical word problems. Specifically, it aims to determine how these factors influence teachers' views and practices:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Length of Service
 - 1.4 Designation
2. What are the perceptions of the respondents on the challenges learners face and the teaching strategies used in problem solving involving multiplication and addition in terms of:
 - 2.1. *Conceptual Understanding*
 - 2.2. *Computational Skills*
 - 2.3. *Problem Comprehension*
 - 2.4. *Instructional Adaptability and Remedial Intervention*
 - 2.5. *Motivational and Emotional Support*
3. Is there a significant relationship in the respondents' perceptions on learners' challenges and teaching strategies when grouped according to their profile variables?
4. What intervention program could be recommended based on the results?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a quantitative descriptive-correlational design. It described the profile of teacher-respondents in terms of age, gender, length of service, and designation, and examined their perceptions of learners' challenges and teaching strategies in problem solving. ANOVA was employed to determine significant relationship in teachers' perceptions when grouped according to their profile variables.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were Grade 4 to 6 teachers from selected public elementary schools in Javier, Leyte. They were chosen through purposive sampling, targeting teachers directly handling mathematics instruction. This ensured that the participants could provide relevant insights on learners' challenges and the teaching strategies used in problem solving involving addition and multiplication.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in selected public elementary schools within the municipality of Javier, Leyte. The schools were chosen due to their proximity to the researchers, making data gathering more efficient while still representing common classroom contexts where problem-solving challenges in addition and multiplication occur.

Research Instrument

The study employed a structured survey questionnaire with three parts: teachers' profile (age, gender, length of service, designation), learners' performance (conceptual understanding, computational skills, problem comprehension), and teaching strategies (instructional adaptability with remedial interventions, motivational and emotional support). All items used a Likert scale and were validated by the researcher's adviser for clarity and reliability.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before distributing the questionnaires, the researchers sought approval from the school heads by sending formal request letters. Once permission was granted, the validated survey forms were distributed to the identified respondents. After collection, the responses were encoded, organized, and subjected to statistical analysis. Confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were strictly maintained throughout the process.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The study strictly followed ethical standards to protect the rights of respondents. Permission was obtained from school authorities, and informed consent was secured from respondents who participated voluntarily with the option to withdraw anytime. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained, with data stored securely for academic use only. Researchers ensured fairness, respect, and integrity, presenting findings honestly and objectively.

Likert Scale

- 4 – Strongly Agree
- 3 – Agree
- 2 – Disagree
- 1 – Strongly Disagree

Mean Scores Interpretation

The study used a four-point Likert scale where mean scores from 3.25 to 4.00 were interpreted as Strongly Agree, 2.50 to 3.24 as Agree, 1.75 to 2.49 as Disagree, and 1.00 to 1.74 as Strongly Disagree.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results of data analysis and interpretation based on the study's problems and hypotheses. Using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), it determines significant differences in teaching strategies and competence across demographic groups. Data are presented through tables with descriptive interpretations to provide clarity and meaningful insights.

What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of:

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Age

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
55-65	3	10.00
45-54	9	30.00
35-44	8	26.67
34 YEARS OLD and BELOW	10	33.33
TOTAL	30	100.00

Table 1 shows that most of the 30 teacher-respondents in Javier, Leyte are young to mid-career. Ten respondents (33.33%) were aged 34 and below, nine (30.00%) were aged 45–54, eight (26.67%) were aged 35–44, and only three (10.00%) were aged 55–65, indicating a generally youthful workforce.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Gender

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MALE	5	16.67
FEMALE	25	83.33
TOTAL	30	100.00

As shown in Table 2, most of the 30 teacher-respondents in Javier, Leyte are female, with 25 or 83.33% of the total. Only five respondents, or 16.67%, are male, indicating that teaching in the area is largely a female-dominated profession.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Length of Service

LENGTH OF SERVICE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1 TO 3	5	16.67
4 TO 6	1	3.33
7 TO 9	6	20.00
ABOVE 10 YEARS	18	60.00
TOTAL	30	100.00

Table 3 shows that most of the 30 teacher-respondents in Javier, Leyte have over 10 years of teaching experience, totaling 18 or 60.00%. Six teachers (20.00%) have 7 to 9 years, five (16.67%) have 1 to 3 years, and one (3.33%) has 4 to 6 years, indicating a highly experienced teaching group.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Designation

DESIGNATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
T1	5	16.67
T2	0	0.00
T3	25	83.33
MT1	0	0.00
MT2	0	0.00
MT3	0	0.00
TOTAL	30	100.00

Table 4 shows that most of the 30 teacher-respondents in Javier, Leyte hold the position of Teacher III, comprising 25 or 83.33% of the group, while 5 (16.67%) are Teacher I. No respondents were classified as Teacher II or Master Teachers, indicating a predominantly mid-level teaching workforce.

What are the perceptions of the respondents on the challenges learners face and the teaching strategies used in problem solving involving multiplication and addition in terms of:

- 2.1. *Conceptual Understanding*
- 2.2. *Computational Skills*
- 2.3. *Problem Comprehension*
- 2.4. *Instructional Adaptability and Remedial Intervention*
- 2.5. *Motivational and Emotional Support*

To address this question, the following indicators were examined:

A. Challenges Learners Face in Problem Solving

Table 2.1: Perceptions on Conceptual Understanding

	CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING	MEAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1	Many learners fail to understand the meaning behind mathematical operations.	2.43	DISAGREE
2	Learners often memorize steps without understanding why they are used.	2.67	AGREE

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3	Many students struggle to connect math concepts to real-life situations.	2.57	AGREE
4	Learners confuse when and how to use addition versus multiplication.	2.47	DISAGREE
5	Even after repeated explanations, many learners still do not grasp key concepts.	2.63	AGREE
	OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.554	AGREE

The findings show that learners' main struggle is not with basic operations but with understanding and applying mathematical concepts. Many rely on memorizing steps without grasping their purpose, which makes it difficult to connect ideas to real-life situations or retain concepts even after repeated teaching. This reveals a deeper problem of limited conceptual foundations, suggesting the need for teaching strategies that emphasize comprehension, connections, and application rather than rote learning.

Table 2.2: Perceptions on Computational Skills

	COMPUTATIONAL SKILLS	MEAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1	Most of my students can solve routine addition and multiplication problems but become lost when faced with unfamiliar or contextual word problems.	2.83	AGREE
2	I have learners who rely heavily on guessing answers instead of understanding the problem.	3.03	STRONGLY AGREE
3	My students often lack confidence and struggle with critical thinking when solving multi-step problems.	2.57	AGREE
4	I frequently encounter students who give up easily once they don't understand a problem right away.	3	AGREE

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5	Many learners only focus on the numbers in the problem and ignore the questions being asked.	3.03	AGREE
	OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.892	AGREE

The findings show that while students manage routine computations, they struggle with unfamiliar and contextual problems. Many rely on guessing, focus only on numbers instead of questions, and give up easily when challenged. They also show low confidence and weak critical thinking in multi-step tasks. The core problem is that learners have basic skills but lack deeper problem-solving ability and persistence.

Table 2.3: Perceptions on Problem Comprehension

	PROBLEM COMPREHENSION	MEAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1	A significant number of learners make frequent computation errors	2.7	AGREE
2	Learners take a long time to finish basic tasks.	2.77	AGREE
3	Many rely on fingers or objects for solving problems.	2.57	AGREE
4	Most students struggle to compute accurately and tend to work slowly.	2.3	DISAGREE
5	Learners lack confidence in mental math	2.83	AGREE
	OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.634	AGREE

The results indicate that learners experience notable challenges in problem comprehension. Although there is some disagreement that most struggle with accuracy and speed, the overall mean of 2.63 (Agree) highlights that the main problem lies in slow performance, reliance on concrete aids, and weak confidence, which hinder learners from developing strong problem comprehension skills.

B. Teaching Strategies Used

Table 2.4: Perceptions on INSTRUCTIONAL ADAPTABILITY & REMEDIAL INTERVENTIONS

	INSTRUCTIONAL ADAPTABILITY & REMEDIAL INTERVENTIONS	MEAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1	I usually stick to the same teaching methods across topics and classes, even when lessons vary in difficulty.	2.95	AGREE
2	I often continue with the next lesson without repeating previous ones or ensuring mastery.	2.9	AGREE
3	I rarely use visual aids, manipulatives, or real-life connections when teaching.	2.73	AGREE
4	I rely mainly on regular class instruction and the same set of activities for all learners, regardless of progress.	2.82	DISAGREE
5	I generally provide support to the class as a group, observing learning gaps only through overall participation.	2.65	AGREE
	OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.81	AGREE

The data with an overall mean of 2.81 interpreted as Agree reveal that teachers tend to prioritize curriculum completion rather than ensuring mastery. This shows that speed of coverage is valued more than depth of understanding, which results in learners who finish topics but remain weak in problem solving with addition and multiplication.

Table 2.5: Perceptions on Motivational and Emotional Support

	MOTIVATION AND EMOTIONAL SUPPORT	MEAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1	I use praise and encouragement regularly.	3.53	STRONGLY AGREE
2	I allow some to pass to keep them motivated.	2.5	AGREE
3	I value and praise effort as well as correct answers.	3.37	STRONGLY AGREE
4	Learners are more engaged when they feel emotionally supported.	3.4	STRONGLY AGREE
5	I stop helping learners who continually fail.	3.47	STRONGLY AGREE
	OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.254	STRONGLY AGREE

With an overall mean of 3.25 (Strongly Agree), data show teachers value motivation and emotional support through praise and encouragement. While they believe these foster participation and interest, many admit stopping help for repeatedly failing learners, revealing a gap between intent and practice that may hinder confidence and problem-solving.

3. Is there a significant relationship in the respondents' perceptions on learners' challenges, and teaching strategies in problem solving involving multiplication and addition when grouped according to their profile variables (age, gender, length of service, and designation)?

Table 3.1: Significant Relationship in Learners' Challenges and Teacher's Teaching Strategies According to Age

VARIABLES	F-VALUE	SIG	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
Conceptual Understanding	1.132	0.355	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Computational Skills	0.059	0.981	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Problem Comprehension	0.548	0.654	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Instructional Flexibility and Remedial Support	1.551	0.225	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Motivational and Emotional Support	0.539	0.660	Accept H_0	Not Significant

The results in Table 3.1 show no significant relationship between learners' challenges and teachers' strategies across all variables, indicating that teacher age does not affect how strategies are applied in addressing student needs.

Table 3.2: Significant Relationship in Learners' Challenges and Teacher's Teaching Strategies According to Gender

VARIABLES	F-VALUE	SIG	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
Conceptual Understanding	0.273	0.606	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Computational Skills	1.183	0.286	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Problem Comprehension	0.493	0.488	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Instructional Flexibility and Remedial Support	0.213	0.648	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Motivational and Emotional Support	0.004	0.952	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Findings in Table 3.2 show no significant relationship between learners' challenges and teachers' strategies by gender, indicating that gender does not influence how strategies address understanding, computation, comprehension, flexibility, or motivation.

Table 3.3: Significant Relationship in Learners' Challenges and Teacher's Teaching Strategies According to Length of Service

VARIABLES	F-VALUE	SIG	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
Conceptual Understanding	0.362	0.781	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Computational Skills	0.664	0.582	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Problem Comprehension	1.258	0.309	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Instructional Flexibility and Remedial Support	0.927	0.442	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Motivational and Emotional Support	0.228	0.876	Accept H_0	Not Significant

The results in Table 3.3 show no significant relationship between learners' challenges and teachers' teaching strategies across all variables when grouped according to length of service. This indicates that years of teaching experience do not affect how strategies are applied in addressing learners' challenges and teaching strategies.

Table 3.4: Significant Relationship in Learners' Challenges and Teacher's Teaching Strategies According to Designation

VARIABLES	F-VALUE	SIG	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
Conceptual Understanding	0.683	0.415	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Computational Skills	0.386	0.540	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Problem Comprehension	0.493	0.488	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Instructional Flexibility and Remedial Support	0.129	0.723	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Motivational and Emotional Support	2.248	0.145	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Findings in Table 3.4 show no significant relationship between learners' challenges and teachers' strategies by designation, indicating that a teacher's rank does not affect how strategies are applied to address conceptual understanding, computation, problem comprehension, flexibility, or motivation.

SUMMARY

The teacher-respondents in Javier, Leyte are mostly young to middle-aged and predominantly female, with most holding the rank of Teacher III and none at the Master Teacher level. Findings show no significant relationship between their demographic profile and learners' performance or teaching strategies. Despite differences in age, gender, designation, and experience, teaching practices remain similar, and learning outcomes continue to be affected by the pressure to complete the curriculum. Students are often promoted without full mastery, resulting in weak understanding and low readiness, while limited remediation and repetitive instruction lead to incomplete learning progress.

CONCLUSION

This study reveals that learners' poor performance in solving mathematical word problems results not only from limited skills but also from systemic flaws in teaching practices driven by the pressure to complete the curriculum and maintain teacher profiles. Instruction often follows rigid and repetitive methods that provide little support for struggling students. The reliance on a scripted curriculum emphasizes lesson coverage over mastery, leading to weak comprehension, low confidence, and poor persistence. Education thus becomes a system of compliance rather than competence. To address this, schools must prioritize learner growth by removing the scripted curriculum, allowing teacher flexibility, and promoting mastery-based instruction. Advancement should depend on demonstrated understanding, while classroom observations must focus on authentic teaching practices. Trainings and seminars should ensure the actual application of strategies so that education moves from maintaining appearances to fostering meaningful learning and effective problem-solving skills.

REFERENCES

- Boaler, J. (2019). *Mathematical mindsets: Unleashing students' potential through creative math, inspiring messages, and innovative teaching*. Jossey-Bass.
- Capuyan, D. (2019). Mathematics remedial program for elementary learners in Cebu City, Philippines. *American Research Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(5), 1–11. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1391536.pdf>
- Department of Education. (2021). *Most essential learning competencies (MELCs)*. Department of Education Philippines. <https://www.deped.gov.ph>
- Fuchs, L. S., Fuchs, D., & Stecker, P. M. (2021). Supporting mathematical problem solving among students with mathematics difficulties. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 54(5), 322–334. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022219421998930>
- Hussein, S., & Csíkos, C. (2023). Elementary students' approaches to mathematical problem solving: A cross-national study. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 21(3), 567–586. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-022-10256-1>
- Lumbao, E. (2022). Adaptive teaching strategies and learner engagement in mathematics: Evidence from Philippine classrooms. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 10(8), 15–28. <https://www.ijern.com/journal/2022/August-2022/02.pdf>
- Powell, S. R. (2020). The role of conceptual understanding in solving word problems:

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Implications for elementary mathematics instruction. *Elementary School Journal*, 120(4), 631–655. <https://doi.org/10.1086/708296>

Schunk, D. H., & DiBenedetto, M. K. (2020). Motivation and social-emotional learning: Theory, research, and practice. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 60, 101830. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2019.101830>

Yang, D. C. (2021). Improving problem-solving performance of elementary school students through concept-based instruction. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 106(2), 201–219. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-020-09965-9>

Philippine Business for Education. (2023, June 22). Many public school teachers resorting to mass promotion, PBEEd says. *Philstar Global*. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/06/22/2275639/4-out-10-learners-drop-out-grade-10>

UNICEF Philippines. (2022). Longitudinal research, policy insights, and recommendations: Evidence from the Philippines basic education system. UNICEF Philippines. <https://www.unicef.org/philippines/media/4596/file/UNIPH-2022-longitudinalresearch-policyinsightsrecommendations.pdf>

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